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AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION OF EMPLOYEES BEHAVIOUR AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IMPLEMENTATION IN THE PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS

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Abstract: Technology gaining grounds in the emerging world of corporates, banks are highly open to welcome the sophistication in operations. They are the significant institutions for an economy and so are the employees. The perspective of the human resource is highly demanding in the emerging trends of an economy. This study aimed towards employee's behaviour and customer satisfaction for the artificial intelligence environment implementation for fulfilling the framed objectives the primary data is considered in this study which is being collected from the employees and customers associated with the private banks of the Jhansi district of Uttar Pradesh state. The data is being analysed with the help of Pearson correlation, Automatic Linear regression modelling, chi-square and Linear regression. The findings of the study revealed that high grade A.I. tools helped in gaining the customer satisfaction in the private sector banks which can also be depends on the extraneous variables, further the employee's behaviour is highly impacting with the high grade/segment technology deployed in the organisation, it is also found that leaves substitution interface is highly appreciated in the workplaces. Employers are recommended to introduce the high-grade technologies in the workplaces with subsequent feedback from the employees towards the A.I. technology.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, employees' behaviour, customer satisfaction, organisation, Human resource.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is regaining the emergence in the world of corporates and business that enhancing the innovation and productivity which assist to imagine the growth of the organization(Vajpayee & Ramachandran, 2019). The utility of AI to enhance the performance of the products, processes and decision-taking. The availability of the technology in today's world helps the organisation to attain the agility powered AI(Zemánková, 2022). The leaders in the organization need to bring out the changes in the particular areas, figure out the complexity where

A.I(Odeh, 2023). could help in achieving goals of the company and the growth perspective. The significance of A.I. is being observed in the entire economies consist of several industries. Now a days A.I. is helpful in education, transportation, operations, marketing, human resource, internet of things, health and what not(Soria Zurita et al., 2022). A.I. helps in preventing many of the cyber disasters by generating algorithms, prediction & forecasting and detecting anomalies. A.I(Raisch & Krakowski, 2021). automation process helps in reducing the interference of intensive labour and tediousness task engagements(Schrettenbrunner, 2020). The success of implementation of artificial intelligence environment in the organisation is highly depending on the people who are running the organisation i.e. employees(Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0), 2023). The behind the relation is that only employees would be affected either negatively or positively, so it is significant to study employee's behaviour for the part of implementation of artificial intelligence environment in the organisation(Konovalova et al., 2022). There are certain notion and findings towards the implementation of the A.I. environment, no doubt it helps in the automation of the working which predominantly impacts the behaviour of the employees working towards a certain cause(Toorajipour et al., 2021). There are many variables which influences employees towards the A.I. environment but this study is focused only on the few variables which are as follows:

1. Customer satisfaction
2. High grade A.I. environment
3. Human need in handling A.I.
4. Time saving
5. Data verification
6. Maintenance of environment
7. Conduct of employees
8. Contribution of employees
9. Feedback system
10. Leaves framework
11. Targets compliances

The behaviour of the employees will be judged on the basis of the responses collected from the current employees of the organisation on the above-mentioned parameters which assumes the entire behaviour of the employees towards the A.I. environment in the organisation(Dopfer, 1991). On the part of the organisation only private sector banks are being targeted for the study the underlying reason for this is the number of private sector bank is higher than the public sector bank which results in the increase of the study area(Konovalova et al., 2022). Bank is the basic economic engine for an economy it creates supply of the money which enhances the demand and further helps in the building of the GDP of the country so, it is predominantly significant to conduct a

study on the banking industry of the country which is contributing in the financial structure of the nation being on the front end(Zarghami & Dumrak, 2021).

In the recent studies it is found that sophisticated high level employee behaviour is profoundly impacting in the decision-making part of the employees which are indirectly A.I assisted(Cabrera et al., 2023). Exploring the fields of the management, Artificial Intelligence is not lacking behind the disciplines, it assists marketing function, Human resource function which implies that it creates simplification and precisely executes work which is less prone in creating errors (Garg et al., 2021). Errors are sometimes created by adhering to the unethical instructions from the supervisors. Now, supervisors could be anyone either it is A.I. or Human interference, which can make the process of management critical to execute. (Lanz et al., 2024) Understanding human behaviour, preferences, choice, satisfaction, expectation falls within a paraphrase of management functions. It is found that customer behaviour is being less impacting the A.I. functions and execution but customer satisfaction is a variable which is highly significant for the case of A.I.(R. & VK, 2021) Employees are the significant part of the organisation and s is the attrition rate, Artificial intelligence profoundly found helpful for assessing employees requirement for the organisation, it assess the efficiency, involvement, attitude and behaviour of the employees towards the organisation which is highly impactful for the part of HR functions to have an insight that which employee is need to retain.(Ria Emilia Sari, 2020) Retention of employees is highly unpredictable in today's world of dynamism, it is already encountered that employees now a days are not even happy with all the high grade services provided by an organisation resulting that he/she keep on changing the job frequently which incurs crores of losses to the firms and the industries, A.I. on these days are working towards increasing employees retention which helps in benefiting firms and their financial stability. (Rao et al., 2020)

OBJECTIVES:

1. To analyse the relationship between customer satisfaction and high grade A.I. tools implementation.
2. To investigate how employees' behaviour is changing towards the adoption of A.I. tools.

HYPOTHESES

H₀: There is no significant relationship between customer satisfaction and high grade A.I. tools implementation.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between customer satisfaction and high grade A.I. tools implementation.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between employee behaviour and A.I. tools adoption.

H₁: There is no significant relationship between employee behaviour and A.I. tools adoption.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study is profoundly a part of human resource management field having a touch of computer science. The objective of the study is being fulfilled with a help of primary data collected from the bank employees which can be of managerial designation as well as non-managerial designation, who have given the consent on themselves to respond to a designated questionnaire/schedule which is specific for the study objectives. It is already being ensured that respondents must be having sound health condition for the unbiased data collection(Shona, 2020).

Subjects

The process of data collection is being started with the distribution of the well-structured questionnaire to the employees working and active customers in the private sector banks in the Jhansi district of the Uttar Pradesh state of India, which includes private sector commercial banks namely ICICI BANK, HDFC BANK, RBL BANK, YES BANK, and INDUSIND BANK. the total number of 250 questionnaire were distributed out of which only 208 were received back in which few are fully filled while few are incomplete. After the cleaning process only 208 questionnaires were found to be valid for the purpose of data analysis and validation. The age of the study group is varied between 21-40 years in which 136 were females and 72 were males the study is being dominated by the female respondents. The respondents are carrying a mixed profile in which the highest degree for qualification is found to be doctorate. The sample is consisting of the people from managerial and managerial positions in which only 41 people were found to be managers and rest are form the non-managerial positions. The mean number of experience years person are having is 4.1 years while mean number of years of education is found to be 16.10.

Outcome variables

The questionnaire is consisting of the 35 items which are designated to analyse the behaviour of the employees towards the A.I. environment in the organisation. 15 questions are based on the demography characteristics of the population and rest are the variable based questions which are being prepared with a help of the expert's advice, experts are purely from the academics having more than 10 years of the experience. The variable questions are based on the 5-point Likert scale having a scale varies from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Thereafter the questions related to the factors affecting employee's behaviour towards the A.I. tools and environment. Which are as follows: 1) High grade tools used in the organisation for the benefit of the employees which relatively consumes lesser time to accomplish the objective or complete the task. 2) Human need after the anticipation of the A.I. environment in the organisation. 3) time saving functions performed by the A.I. interface. 4) Verification of the work completed by the A.I. with a human intelligence. 5) maintenance of the A.I. tool by the employees for the longer support. 6) change in the conduct of the employees after the introduction of the A.I. interface in the organisation. 7)

contribution of the employees while working with the A.I. environment in the organisation. 8) feedbacks given by the employees for the A.I. support interception provided by the employer for the efficient and effective working. 9) Leaves taken by the employees and support provided by the A.I. interface to fill up the void created by the absence of the employee in the organisation. 10) targets completed by the employees on time and the quality of the performance with the help of A.I. interface(Munshi, 2014). The internal consistency of the questionnaire is being checked and it is found that the Cron Bach Alpha is achieved the accepted value i.e. of .836.

Statistical Analysis

The hypothesis of the study is being checked with the help of number of tests in which Automatic linear modelling is first to be used with linear regression which is being followed to investigate the relationship between dependent and independent variables and Pearson correlation is also used to check the degree of association between the variables in the hypothesis(Yandell & Ryan, 1998). To test the other hypothesis chi-square measure is being used to check the association between the variable(Yeager, 2022)s. To confirm the internal consistency Cron Bach Alpha measure is also being used. The entire analysis part is being performed on the SPSS version 20.

RESULTS

The objectives of the study are focused on the exploring the connect of High grade A.I. tools with the satisfaction of the customers which is highly subjective to what is the experience a customer is gaining by encountering the A.I. tools. The collected is analysed for the variable like customer satisfaction and high grade A.I. technology uses. The table 1 is based on the internal consistency and reliability test where Cronbach Alpha test is used to check the validity of the data and it is found that the Alpha value is falling under the acceptable limit i.e. between .70 to .90. The value is .836(Nihan, 2020).

TABLE 1: CRONBACH ALPHA RELIABILITY TEST

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.834	.836	11

Source: Prepared by Authors

The linear regression model is applied on these two variables where customer satisfaction is a dependent variable and high grade A.I. technology is independent variable. In table 2 it is found

that the Pearson correlation (R-value) between both the variables is found to be 0.6 which reflects the strong correlation value.

TABLE 2: PEARSON CORRELATION

Correlations

		customer satisfaction	high grade
Pearson Correlation	customer satisfaction	1.000	.627
	high grade	.627	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	customer satisfaction	.	.000
	high grade	.000	.
N	customer satisfaction	129	129
	high grade	129	129

Source: Prepared by Authors

TABLE 3: REGRESSION MODEL SUMMARY

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.627 ^a	.393	.388	.905	.393	82.283	1	127	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), high grade

Source: Prepared by Authors

The value of R-Square is found to be 0.393 indicates how much percentage of the total variation in the dependent variable, can be explained by the independent variable, the value is quite low i.e. 39%. This justifies that there could also be another variable which affects the dependent variables and impacting the study objectives in majority.

This table 3, indicates that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly well, this indicates the statistical significance of the regression model that was run. Here, $p < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05, and indicates that, overall, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable (i.e., it is a good fit for the data).

TABLE 4: ANOVA TABLE

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	67.442	1	67.442	82.283	.000 ^b
Residual	104.093	127	.820		
Total	171.535	128			

Source: Prepared by Authors

The other objective of the study is centred on the change in employee’s behaviour towards the adoption of A.I. tools.

After putting data on the analysis part, the automatic linear modelling is used to find out the frequency of the above-mentioned factor affecting the behaviour of the employee towards the A.I. tools. As we can see in figure 1, that high grade is the factor which is found to be highly influencing the behaviour of the in-house employees, ease of leave allocation system is found to second most highly impacting variable for this cause, further feedbacks, time-saving and maintenance is also found to be impacting significantly as compared to the other variables.

FIGURE 1: AUTOMATIC LINEAR MODELLING

Source: Prepared by Authors

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study deals with the factors influencing employee's behaviour towards the A.I. environment implementation in the organisation. Although behaviour of the any individual is determined by the number of factors in which organisation plays a major role in determining the same. There are number of factors taken in the study in determining employee's behaviour i.e. High grade, Human need, timesaving, verification, maintenance, conduct, contribution, feedback, leaves, targets. The first objective of the study is focused on the relationship between customer satisfaction and high grade A.I. tools implementation, data given by the employees and the customers analysed as per the hypothesis and it is found that null hypothesis for the first objective is rejected i.e. there is a relationship between customer satisfaction and high grade A.I. tool implementation, there is a high positive correlation between both of the variables. Which simply means that customer appreciates the A.I. tools implementation, so the higher implementation leads to the higher customer satisfaction which also helps organisation to retain its customer base and it could also attract the other individuals to such banks as their bankers. The other objective of the study is centred on the relationship between employee's behaviour towards the A.I. tools implementation. According to the factors taken in the study which affects behaviour of the employees it is found that high grade A.I. tools which is implementing in the organisation mostly affects the employees, as compared to other factors, after the intensity of the high grade, the substitution of A.I. during the leaves of the employees is appreciated and affects the employees in the organisation, the reason could be that work and task should not be affected during the leaves of the employees, it is also being found that employees need to be in contact at some point of time for the works going on in the organisation during his/her leave period. Which mostly creates frustration among the employees, so this issue can be solved with a help of A.I. environment implementation. After the leave framework, feedback, time-saving and maintenance of the A.I. tools are also significantly influencing the employee's behaviour. The feedback system of A.I. is purely unbiased, which helps employees to be away from the organisational politics and left them to be relaxed. This is highly appreciable among the employees to work fearlessly with their efficiency levels. The time-saving feature provide by the A.I. is also gaining importance in the corporate world, it creates difference in the employee's lives. The time taken in each of the task is getting reduced which helps employees to work on other tasks in that particular time period only, they can also enjoy the leisure time too. All this results in the improved efficiency on the part of employees this could only be the reason for the influencing behaviour of the employees. The maintenance of the A.I. is also found to be a significant factor which is obviously not a tiring task. Some of the technology failed on the ground level due to a huge effortful maintenance task, which is not in the case of A.I. after getting such flawless outputs employees welcome the maintenance task of the technology. This finding is different from the existing studies where the maintenance task is not so much welcomed by the employees of the organisation. It is recommended that high grade technology should be adopted

in the organisation as it creates a positive environment and confidence among the employees which only results in the higher efficiency levels of the employees. The employee's feedback is highly significant when organisation is planning to induce some new technology because human resources is a significant component for the overall growth of the organisation in the entire industry or the economy.

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